

Oxidimetric Estimation of Caffeine using Aromatic Sulphonyl Haloamines

S. M. MAYANNA* and B. JAYARAM

Department of Chemistry, Central College, Bangalore-560 001

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The reactions between caffeine and *N*-haloamines have been found to proceed quantitatively over a wide range of experimental conditions. Simple titrimetric procedures for the assay of caffeine with *N*-haloamines have been developed. The products of oxidation are identified. The methods are also extended for the assay of caffeine in medicinal formulations, instant coffee and tea, soft drinks and alcoholic beverages.

CONSIDERABLE progress has been made in analytical chemistry with the introduction of aromatic sulphonyl haloamines as redox titrants^{1,2}. *N*-Haloamines react with a surprising range of functional groups, affecting an array of molecular transformations. The well known member of the *N*-haloamines are: chloramine-T (CAT), dichloramine-T (DCT), bromamine-T (BAT), dibromamine-T (DBT), chloramine-B (CAB), dichloramine-B (DCB), bromamine-B (BAB), and dibromamine-B (DBB). The dihalogen compounds are generally employed as redox titrants in non-aqueous or partially aqueous media.

Caffeine (1, 3, 7-trimethylxanthine) is a stimulant present in pharmaceuticals, food products, plant materials and drinks. The analytical procedures reported so far, for its estimation in solution include complexometric titrations³, chromatography⁴, potentiometry⁵ and spectrophotometry⁶. These methods involve sophisticated instrumentation or elaborate experimental procedures. Simple titrimetric procedures are therefore required for assaying caffeine in solution. The present communication reports the oxidimetric estimation of caffeine with DCT, BAT, DBT, CAB, BAB and DCB. A direct titration of the reductant with haloamines was not feasible, but the back titration methods developed are simple, elegant and fairly rapid.

Experimental

Caffeine (B.D.H.) was recrystallised from aqueous solution⁷ before use. Caffeine solution of known concentration was prepared by dissolving the required amount of caffeine in triple-distilled water (for monohaloamines), or glacial acetic acid (for dihaloamines). CAB⁸, DCB⁹, DCT¹⁰, BAB¹¹, BAT¹² and DBT¹³ were prepared and characterised by standard procedures.

Preliminary studies :

A 10⁻⁵ M caffeine solution (5 ml) was added to a known and excess (40-60%) volume of oxidant

(0.005 N) containing various concentrations of HClO₄ (0.01-0.1M) or NaOH (0.01-1.0M) or buffers¹⁴ (pH 1-10) in an iodine-flask. The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time with occasional shaking. 3M H₂SO₄ (20 ml) and 10% KI (10 ml) were then added and the liberated iodine was titrated to a starch end-point with standard Na₂S₂O₃ solution (0.01M). A blank titration was carried out with the oxidants under identical conditions.

In 30 min, the oxidation of caffeine with CAB is stoichiometric in HClO₄ and fairly rapid in buffer media (pH 1 and 2). A slight over-oxidation is noticed in buffers of pH 3 and 4 and slow at pH > 4. The rate of oxidation is very slow in presence of NaOH. Oxidation of caffeine by BAT is more or less stoichiometric in HClO₄. In buffer media, the rate increases at pH > 1, reaches a maximum at pH 3 and then decreases. However, a reproducible stoichiometry is observed in NaOH medium (0.01-0.5M). Oxidation of caffeine by BAB is slow in mineral acids and in buffers (except pH 2, 4 and 5). However, the required stoichiometry is noticed in presence of NaOH (0.5-1.0 M). The oxidation of caffeine by dihaloamines in glacial acetic acid is stoichiometric and reproducible within 30 min.

The results were subjected to statistical analysis. The values of coefficient of variance (%) for different oxidants were in the limit 0.1 to 0.5. From these results it appear that the accuracy of estimation of caffeine with different oxidants is in the order, DCT > DBT > DCB > CAB > BAT = BBB.

Recommended procedure :

A known volume (25 ml) of 0.05 N oxidant was reacted with aliquots of caffeine in an iodine-flask, containing sufficient amount of acid or base (buffer of pH 2 for CAB, 0.025-0.5 M NaOH for BAT, 0.05-1.0 M NaOH for BAB and 25 ml of 50% acetic acid for dihaloamines). After 30 min, 3 M sulphuric acid (20 ml) was added along with 10%

KI (10 ml) and the liberated iodine estimated using standard thiosulphate solution (0.01 N) Blank experiment was conducted at each time, and the amount of caffeine in the sample solution estimated

Preliminary separation for assaying caffeine in different materials :

ACQ (aspirin-caffeine-quinine) tablet : Powdered tablet (0.25 g) was warmed with 0.1N sodium bicarbonate solution (25 ml), filtered and the residue washed. The filtrate was extracted with chloroform (3×30 ml) and the extract washed with dilute hydrochloric acid (1×10⁻³N, 3×30 ml) The residue from the chloroform extract was taken up in distilled water (100 ml) and 10 ml of the solution was used for the estimation with oxidants.

APC (aspirin, phenacetin and caffeine) tablets : Powdered tablet (0.25g) was refluxed with 2N H₂SO₄ (10 ml) for 1 h. The solution was then cooled, diluted with water (10 ml) and extracted with successive portions (30 ml) of chloroform until extraction is complete. The aqueous solution was preserved for the assay of phenacetin. The combined chloroform layer was extracted with 1 N NaOH (3 × 20 ml) and then with water (20 ml) The alkaline extract was then used for the assay of acetyl salicylic acid. The chloroform extract was evaporated and the residue was taken up in 100 ml distilled water and a 10 ml of the solution was taken for the estimation with the oxidants.

AC (aspirin-caffeine) tablet : Powdered tablet (0.25 g) was warmed with 0.1 N sodium bicarbonate solution (25 ml), filtered and the residue then washed. The filtrate was extracted with chloroform (3×30 ml). The solvent was evaporated and the residue dissolved in distilled water (100 ml), and a 10 ml of the solution was used for estimation with the oxidants.

Drinks (alcoholic and non-alcoholic) : The sample (10 ml) with or without added caffeine was treated with liquor ammonia (10 ml) and extracted with chloroform¹⁶ (3 × 20 ml). Chloroform was evaporated, and the concentrate taken up in distilled water (10 ml) was estimated with the oxidants.

Instant coffee : The sample (10 g) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p 40-60°). The dried residue was treated with ammonium hydroxide solution (sp gr. 0.88) and then extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and then filtered through a column containing aluminium oxide and magnesium oxide. The filtrate was evaporated. The solid caffeine was then dissolved in a known volume of water and used for analysis.

Instant tea : Polyphenols, pigments and other substances were removed from a known volume of an aqueous solution of the sample by precipitating with 3% lead subacetate [2Pb(C₂H₃O₂)₂Pb(OH)₂] solution. The filtrate and washings were collected and treated with 2 N H₂SO₄ to remove the excess of lead compound. It was then filtered and the acid

in the solution was neutralised with dilute NaOH. A known volume of this solution was used for estimation with the oxidants

Copper complex : An aqueous acidic solution of copper(II) chloride was added to an aqueous solution of caffeine (8 : 1 mol ratio). The mixture was stirred for several hours when dark green crystals of the complex¹⁷ appeared. They were washed with ether and the dried sample of the complex [CuCl₂(C₈H₁₀N₄O₂)H₂O] was analysed for copper. A known amount of the complex (1 mg ml⁻¹) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and used for estimation with oxidants

Results and Discussion

In order to show the recovery capability of the present method, experiments are carried out containing known amounts (0.50-25 mg) of caffeine. Some typical results are given in Table 1. It is seen that caffeine can be estimated by the *N*-haloamine with an accuracy of about ± 1%. Table 2 indicates the determination of caffeine in various samples. The method of sample preparation described earlier is designed to remove interfering compounds. The results of spectrophotometric analysis are also included for comparison. It is seen that the values obtained by the titrimetric determination using *N*-haloamines are in agreement with those obtained by the spectrophotometric method.

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF CAFFEINE WITH *N*-HALOAMINES

Caffeine taken (mg)	Caffeine found (mg)					
	CAB	BAB	BAT	DCT	DBT	DCB
0.5	0.5	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
1.0	1.01	0.99	1.01	1.00	1.01	0.99
1.5	1.51	1.49	1.51	1.50	1.49	1.51
2.0	2.01	1.98	1.98	2.02	2.02	1.99
3.0	3.02	2.98	2.98	3.02	3.02	2.99
4.0	3.99	3.97	4.03	4.01	4.03	3.98
5.0	5.01	5.04	4.97	4.98	5.02	5.03
7.0	7.02	7.05	7.03	7.03	6.98	7.04
10.0	9.99	10.06	9.96	10.02	9.97	10.02
12.0	12.02	12.07	12.06	11.98	12.03	12.04
15.0	14.98	15.08	15.05	15.03	14.95	15.05
20.0	20.03	19.92	19.94	20.04	19.96	19.94
25.0	25.05	24.85	24.94	25.04	25.05	24.98

The stoichiometric oxidation of caffeine with the *N*-haloamines employed can be represented as

where, R=C₆H₄SO₂, R'=p-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂ and X=Cl or Br. It is observed that the monohaloamines undergo a two-electron change while dihalo compounds undergo a four-electron change in their reactions. In each case, the oxidant is reduced to the respective sulphonamide.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF CAFFEINE IN SAMPLES WITH N-HALOAMINES

Sample	Caffeine found (mg g ⁻¹)					
	CAB ^o	BAB	BAT	DCT	DBT	DCT
APC tablet	62.1 (62.5)	62.0	61.98	62.90	61.99	62.0
AC tablet	39.02 (38.8)	38.4	38.4	38.6	38.50	39.01
AQC tablet	33.8 (34.0)	34.3	33.7	34.2	34.2	33.7
Cola drink ^a	100.9 (101.1)	102.0	102.0	101.5	102.0	100.7
Alcoholic beverage ^a	508.1 (510.0)	515.00	514.0	509.0	512.1	513.0
Instant coffee	37.3 (37.5)	37.2	37.8	37.3	37.2	37.8
Instant tea	26.7 (26.8)	26.6	26.99	26.9	27.0	26.6
Caffeine-copper complex ^a	1.99 (-)	2.0	1.98	2.0	1.99	1.98

^aConcentrations are expressed as $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. ^bWeight = 2.0 mg. ^oCaffeine by spectrophotometric method^o given in parenthesis.

The products are dimethylalloxan and methyl-urea, which were detected¹⁸ by tlc. Benzene sulphonamide formed in the reaction with CAB, BAB and DCB was detected by tlc^o. A mixture of petroleum ether, chloroform and n-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) was the solvent, with iodine as the detecting reagent ($R_f=0.88$). *p*-Toluenesulphonamide, the reduced product of BAT, DCT and DBT was identified¹⁹ by paper chromatography with benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl in ethanol as the spray reagent ($R_f=0.91$).

Detailed investigations showed that (i) foreign ions, such as Na, K, Zn²⁺, Ba²⁺, nitrate, phosphate, chlorate and sulphate (upto ionic strength, 0.2M) have no influence on the rate of oxidation, (ii) addition of chloride ion slightly accelerates the rate of oxidation and (iii) stoichiometry of oxidation is unaffected by the reversal of the addition of the reagents.

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